

FEATURES OF THE COMMUNICATIVE CATEGORY OF EXPRESSION IN TED TALK LECTURES

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ABSTRACT

The article is devoted to identifying the ways of expressing the communicative category of expressiveness in TED talk lectures. The following groups of ways of expressing the studied category were identified: lexical, syntactic, stylistic, non-verbal. All of the stated ways contribute to increasing the success of the TED talk lecture on the conference.

Keywords: communicative category, expressiveness, TED talk lectures.

In modern communicative linguistics, the term “*expressiveness*” implies the expression of emotions in speech through various emotional-evaluative linguistic means, reflecting the speaker’s attitude to what is being communicated. Expressiveness as a constant characteristic of discourse forms the communicative category of expressiveness (or the category of emotionality, emotiveness or intensity), which is expressed using various language means that reflect the presence of emotions in the text.

In this work, we regard the categories of expressiveness, emotionality and intensity as synonyms, however, some authors separate these concepts. In particular, V. L. Kudashina believes that the categories of expressiveness and emotionality are correlated according to the “*general - particular*” scheme and differ in their purpose: according to the author, emotions are spontaneous, since they are based on the involuntary reaction of the speaker, and expression is deliberate, since it is aimed at having the greatest possible impact on addressee [1, p. 117]. Regarding the category of intensity, which, according to N. V. Sokolova, is expressed in the widespread use by the authors of texts of intensifiers (for example, “most”, “very”, “enough”, etc.) [2, p. 70], some authors also distinguish it as a separate category. However, N. F. Khasanova in her work argues that expressiveness itself is a property of the text that conveys meaning with increased intensity and results in emotional enhancement [3, p. 107]. Thus, intensity is one of the characteristics of expressiveness.

The communicative category of expressiveness is, to one degree or another, inherent in all types of discourse and largely depends on the communicative situation: on the intentions of the addresser, his background knowledge, as well as on the linguistic and extralinguistic context of the communicative act [4, p. 162]. This category can be expressed by various linguistic means, such as expressive nouns, adjectives and verbs; intensifiers; phraseological units; interjections; as well as non-linguistic means, such as the use of italics and capital letters (written text); gestures; laughter; raising the tone/volume of the voice etc.

Thus, in each type of discourse, the communicative category of expressiveness manifests itself with the help of units of different levels of language, forming a system for expressing expressiveness in speech. This system, according to I. A. Skripak, includes expressive

elements, that is, lexical means that form the basis of this system, as well as syntactic means related to its periphery [5, p. 253]. Thus, in different types of discourse this category will manifest itself with varying degrees of expression, using certain lexical and syntactic means. For example, in conversational discourse, lexical means of expressing the category of expressiveness include the use of interjections and profanity (curse words), and syntactic means include repetitions and changes in word order; in scientific discourse, lexical and syntactic (used more often in this type of discourse) means of expressing the category of expressiveness can include the use of intensifiers, intensifying adverbs and exclamatory constructions, rhetorical questions.

However, despite the representation of the communicative category of expressiveness in all types of discourse, recently this topic has attracted much attention from researchers of media discourse. According to O. Yu. Sergeeva and N. V. Savartseva, this attention is associated with the increased interest of linguists in “the emotional sphere of personality, the problem of the influencing power of words and the possibility of studying a person’s personal qualities through his speech activity” [4, p. 162]. In other words, in the media discourse the category of expressiveness is especially prominent, in connection with the genre characteristics of media texts, and also performs not only the function of expressing emotions, but also expressing personal qualities of a person, the function of influencing the addressee through emotional influence on him. Consequently, the category of expressiveness is especially important for media discourse, since it increases the overall emotionality of the text, reflects the personality of the author, which helps create a trusting “author-addressee” relationship. In addition, with the help of means of expressing the category of expressiveness, the author of a media text draws attention to certain parts of it, which affects the overall perception of the text and the impression of his work.

Thus, **the purpose of this work** is to determine ways of expressing the category of expressiveness in TED talk lectures, which are a separate genre of media discourse [6, 7]. Despite the fact that at the moment there are a number of sources devoted to the category of expressiveness in media discourse, we have not identified any works describing the ways of expressing this

category in lectures of the TED talk format, which determines the scientific novelty and relevance of this article.

A TED talk is a presentation by speakers on a small stage in the United States on relevant topics, with the goal of attracting public attention to a particular social or scientific problem and encouraging the audience to take certain actions, for example, to participate in environmental protection movement [6, p. 140]. Video recordings of the presentations are posted on the corresponding website of the private non-profit TED foundation, that is the initiator and founder of these lectures, and are available for free. The TED lecture genre not only informs and explains information based on scientific research and evaluations, but also entertains the viewer due to its features, such as a relatively free style of speech, clear and accessible presentation of scientific ideas, close connection with the audience, and the use of visual materials and convenient video format [7, p. 76]. Thus, such a public lecture turns into a discourse-generating media genre of a special type [8, p. 258], and represents a separate speech genre of media discourse, different from other popular science genres and types of lectures.

The expressiveness of TED talk lectures is determined by the following factors: the artistry of the speakers; a format similar to a performance; the need to constantly attract the attention of the audience and entertain them; the emotionality of the speaker due to the fact that the topic of the lecture is always especially important and close to him or her. All this determines the frequent use of means of expressing the communicative category of expressiveness in the process of the TED talk speeches.

Based on the analysis of texts and video recordings of lectures from 2021-2023, we have identified the following ways of expressing the category of expressiveness in TED talk lectures, which were divided into four categories: *lexical, syntactic, stylistic and non-verbal*.

1. Lexical ways of expressing

1) *the use of interjections (oh, ah, hey, well, dear etc.)*.

With the help of interjections, the lecturer not only expresses his or her own emotions, but also attracts the attention of the audience, and also reduces the formality of the lecture, simplifying its perception by listeners: “*I remember thinking in that moment “Oh, I finally got a seat at the table” <...> I remember thinking, “Oh, I’m going to talk at this table” (Lilly Singh – “A seat at the table” isn’t the solution for gender equity); “God, I felt like I had just been inducted into the coolest club possible” (Christina Tosi – “My secret to creating real magic); “Well, for starters, we know that the ocean is already doing a lot for us” (Susan Ruffo – “The ocean’s ingenious climate solutions”).*

2) *the use of intensifiers and intensifying adverbs (very, extremely, deeply, highly, strongly, absolutely etc.)*.

The use of intensifiers increases the overall emotionality of speech and the author’s personal attitude to what was said: “*Today their incomes are in and out of poverty, which is extremely painful*” (Sathya Raghu

Mokkapati – “The “Greenhouse-in-a-box” empowering farmers in India”); “*The way it infiltrated society is a clear example of how deeply ingrained racism in this country*” (Dwan Reece “The origins of blackface and Black stereotypes”; “*One thing is absolutely clear: we cannot keep rescuing people from prison and restoring them to poverty*” (Brittany K. Barnett – “The creativity, innovation and ingenuity languishing in US prisons”).

3) *the use of slang and informal language*.

In the analyzed lectures, we noted the widespread use of informal language and profanity, for example slang, curses, hybrid words (words consisting of several parts belonging to different languages), which is unacceptable in many types of discourse: “*I found the “queenas” [“Queen” from the English word “Queen” and the Spanish word “Reina” (queen)] tucked in a dingy bar on 16th street*” (Julian Delgado Ropera – “The poetry of everyday language”); “*My caseload ballooned from 30 to over 100*” (Rebecca Darwent – “How to fund the real change in your community”); “*She <...> whipped up a hell of a cranberry sauce from assorted jelly packets*” (Brittany K. Barnett – “The creativity, innovation and ingenuity languishing in US prisons”); “*It’s the patriarchy that’s so damn difficult*” (Kaz – “Sex education should start with consent”); “*It’s what every motivational poster, Tumblr post, Instagram account you follow, business card tells us: success is a seat at the table. And if they want to be extra spicy [spicy, used as “sassy” (slang)], they say “if there is no seat, drag your own seat*” (Lilly Singh – “A seat at the table” isn’t the solution for gender equity”); “*You know, the digital space had always been a place that I thought was without gatekeepers*” [gatekeeper – a modern concept emerging from social media. Denotes a person who devalues the opinions of others about something by claiming that they have no right to that opinion because they are not qualified/are not legitimate decision makers/are not part of a particular social group, etc.] (Lilly Singh – “A seat at the table” isn’t the solution for gender equity”).

The methods of expressing the category of expressiveness in TED talk lectures mentioned above imply the use of certain words or expressions that have a pronounced emotional connotation, raising the overall level of expressiveness of the lecture. Despite the fact that lexical ways of expressing the category of expressiveness are not characteristic of scientific and popular science texts due to certain limitations of the norms of scientific discourse [5, p. 253], they are widely used in the lectures we analyzed, which emphasizes the uniqueness of TED talk lectures as a genre and their belonging to media discourse.

2. Syntactic ways of expressing

1) *the use of inversion and emphatic constructions*.

The use of stylistic inversion and emphatic constructions in English is often determined by the speaker’s desire to attract the listeners’ attention to a certain part of the utterance. In TED talk lectures, sentences with inversion are pronounced by speakers with great emotion, which reflects not only the need to emphasize certain words and phrases in the text, but also emphasizes the personal interest of the speaker: “*Not*

only is spirit found within us, it's in all things" (Sasha Sarago – "The (de)colonizing of beauty"); "Not only do we not get to hear his point of view, we don't get to share ours" (Betty Hart – "How compassion could save your strained relationships"); "And have we ever decided to use that tool of empathy, of walking a mile or so in someone else's shoes" (Betty Hart – "How compassion could save your strained relationships"); "Now power-to-X is not a new technology, nor did we invent it" (Jim Hagemann Snabe – "Dreams and details for a decarbonized future").

The use of emphatic constructions by lecturers is also due to the need to highlight a certain part of the sentence. For example, the emphatic verb "do" to emphasize the predicate: "I know that donors have good intentions. **I really do**" (Rebecca Darwent – "How to fund the real change in your community"); "Now I don't have the full equation cracked, but **I do know** that it starts with the decision to act" (Christina Tosi – "My Secret to Creating Real Magic"); Identification of circumstances and adverbial subordinate clauses: "**It was at 'Esta Noche'** that I learned about the long history <...> **It was here** that my passion for language bloomed again" (Julian Delgado Ropera – "The poetry of everyday language") etc.

2) The use of exclamatory sentences.

In exclamatory sentences, expressiveness is reflected graphically, using the "!" sign, or orally, using word order as well as intonation and pitch of the voice, and is expressed most clearly. According to A. V. Kerova, exclamatory sentences most often have an emotive-evaluative communicative attitude, [9, p. 180], which allows them to stand out especially against the general background of a popular science TED lecture: "I know you are gluten-free, so here are some almonds for the road! Thank you for your kindness! It goes a long way!" (Ashley M. Grice – "The Power of Purpose in Business"); "We will be able to cross the digital divide, and we will have more jobs, and we will all get that great "Yes! I fixed it!" feeling" (Gay Gordan-Byrne – "You Deserve the Right to Repair Your Stuff"); "Breathe life! Clean air is our right!" (Rosamund Adoo-Kissi-Debrah – "The Tragedy of Air Pollution – and an Urgent Demand for Clean Air"). Such sentences stimulate the attention of listeners, enhance the categorical nature of speech and express the emotions of the author.

3) The use of questions.

Most TED talks use rhetorical questions that do not require a spoken answer from the listener, but require the answer to be thought through. Typically, the author of a lecture asks a rhetorical question related directly to the topic of his lecture, thus drawing attention to it, as well as expressing his special interest. He encourages listeners to answer the question silently, thereby wondering how important it really is to find the answer. Furthermore, in many cases, the answer to the question is given by the speakers themselves during the lecture.: "Isn't it a nice escape from reality and a fun way to think about the world? **It's not**" (Sarah Kurnick – "Aliens build the pyramids" and other absurdities of pseudo-archaeology"); "How do we put the environment at the top of that list? My answer is... we don't"

(Angela Francis – "How to get everyone to care about a green economy"). In addition, using a question helps the speaker not only express his emotions, but also create the impression of spontaneity and flow of the conversation, bringing it closer to dialogue: "So what do you think of when you think of the ocean?" (Susan Ruffo – "The ocean's ingenious climate solutions"); "Would you like to play with me?" Audience: "Yes!" Martin Reeves: "Good. I'm glad you said that" (Martin Reeves – "Why play is essential for business"); Speaker (Ermias Kebreab): "Why not stop eating beef and drinking milk?" Audience member: "Yeah!" (Martin Reeves – "Why play is essential for business").

Thus, it can be noted that syntactic ways of expressing the category of expressiveness, which more typical for popular science lectures, in a TED talk are expressed primarily by the lecturer changing the order of words in a sentence.

3. Stylistic ways of expressing

Stylistic (that is, using stylistic language means) ways of expressing the category of expressiveness are used by lecturers to make the presentation more emotional, thereby distinguishing it from many other lectures at the conference. Due to the nature of the TED conference, where many lectures follow one another, it is important for speakers not only to successfully convey their message to the audience, but also to draw attention to their research or the topic of their talk in general in order to make the most favorable impression on the audience. Thus, with the help of stylistic ways of expressing, the author contributes to the individualization of his lecture, giving it creativity and emotionality. In the analyzed lectures, we identified the following stylistic ways of expressing the studied category:

1) The use of emotionally colored epithets.

"The way we do philanthropy right now, the way we've done it for decades is **broken**" (Rebecca Darwent – "How to fund the real change in your community"); "This is **amazing**. And I'm hopeful that private foundations and donors will follow this **powerful** example" (Rebecca Darwent – "How to fund the real change in your community"); "And I noticed how **weather-worn** and **brittle** and **fragile** they were" (Machine Dazzle – "How to unleash your inner maximalist through costume")

2) The use of phraseological units and set phrases.

"<...> **the silver lining** is that we'll finally get a different perspective in late-night" (Lilly Singh – "A seat at the table" isn't the solution for gender equity"); "<...> **filling out paperwork** and **competing over scraps**" (Rebecca Darwent – "How to fund the real change in your community"); "The light of hope emerges from the depths of darkness" (Sahar Zand – "Why Iranians are cutting their hair for "Woman, life, freedom"); "Communities are left behind and we are **running out of time**" (Rebecca Darwent – "How to fund the real change in your community")

3) The use of metaphor and metonymy.

"That "different" **way of speaking** is a **secret door** only some of us have access to" (Julian Delgado Ropera – "The poetry of everyday language")

4) The use of simile.

“It becomes its own story that you can almost read like a book” (Machine Dazzle – “How to unleash your inner maximalist through costume”); *“Every day it felt as though I was going through the same experience”* (Sahar Zand – “Why Iranians are cutting their hair for “Woman, life, freedom”)

5) *The use of personification.*

“Again, trillions of dollars are sitting just waiting to be put to work” (Rebecca Darwent – “How to fund the real change in your community”); *“My heart sank”* (Julian Delgado Ropera – “The poetry of everyday language”): *“This costume wants to tell a story <...> The costume can be so much more than the costume: it can be the props, it can be the set, it can tell its own stories, it can even be its own character. It can be all of it at the same time”* (Machine Dazzle – “How to unleash your inner maximalist through costume”).

4. Non-verbal ways of expressing

This group of ways of expressing the category of expressiveness is connected with the fact that any TED talk is initially a public speech at a conference, where the speaker needs to present his lecture to the audience from the stage. That is why lecturers try to diversify their presentation and make it more “life-like” and less formal, which helps to establish a connection with the audience and make the lecture easier to perceive.

1) *gestures, moves.*

Such movements and gestures are often unplanned and spontaneous, and also receive positive reactions from listeners: *“I’ve always taken pride in being the kind of artist that’s always making moves”* (Daniel J. Watts – “To accomplish great things, you need to “let the paint dry”) – While pronouncing this phrase, the speaker is dancing.

2) *expression of emotions (laughter, tears, etc.).*

“So now, why am I telling you all this? Well, because my therapist costs 200 dollars an hour, and this [TED talk] is way cheaper” (Lilly Singh – “A seat at the table” isn’t the solution for gender equity”) – After this phrase, the speaker is laughing with the audience.

Conclusions. Thus, the category of expressiveness, which is inherent in any TED talk and expressed in the ways listed above is largely determined by the emotional involvement of the speaker. This involvement evokes the same emotional response in the audience and helps create the trusting relationship between the speaker and the audience, which is an important feature of TED talks and distinguishes them from other scientific and popular science lectures. Using the expressiveness category, lecturers not only show their emotions, but also personalize their lecture, which increases its memorability and competitiveness with other presentations at the conference. In addition, expressiveness helps lecturers draw attention to their topic and individual parts of the speech, placing emphasis in such a way as to facilitate the understanding of

the lecture. Based on this, we can say that in the case of TED talk lectures, the communicative category of expressiveness performs the following functions: expressing the lecturer’s emotions, accentuation (attracting attention and placing emphasis), individualization, establishing a connection with the audience and simplifying the process of understanding the lecture – all of this contributes to increasing the success of TED lecturer.

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